

Post-Covid 19 Pandemic Physical Education Setting with Technology and social media

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic affected the education of about 1.6 billion learners at its height in year 2020, UNESCO (2022) responded immediately introduced new model for international cooperation with telecommunication companies, technology industry, and the mass media. This unique model of collaboration ensures the continuity of educational processes. Educators have adopted social media in education and for other purposes. Studies have confronted that social media used for learning has significant contribution in education (Zhu, 2012). The objective of the study was to determine the effects of the technology and social media on students' performance in physical education. A mixed method in design, descriptive quantitative to acquire data, and a qualitative approach to look into the experiences of the 120 participants, in a locally funded university in the City of Manila, 1st Semester of SY 2023-2024. Based on the results and findings the students in different PE classes used different technology and social media. Open communication, quick information accessibility, acquired informative videos and search international scientific references were the experiences beneficial to students accomplished task activities came-out in the interviews. Technology and social media supplemented the teaching of physical education in this post pandemic era.

Keywords: post COVID-19 pandemic, physical education setting, technology and social media

INTRODUCTION

After the COVID-19 pandemic, many are expecting the educational setting to go back to the old system of classroom teaching and learning situation, but according to the study of Dayagbil et. al. (2021), that the emerging responses to include the trajectory for flexible learning delivery and the role of digital technology scenario provided the contextual basis for strategic actions to ensure continuity to migrate to flexible teaching and learning modality recalibrate the curriculum, capacitate the faculty, upgrade the infrastructure, implement and assess all aspects of educational landscape. Concerns around the educational processes, digital technology become heightened in this post-pandemic that reveals the positive role of technology and social media the way it has become increasingly popular (Das et.al., 2020).

Grob-Zakhary (2020) said that what comes with this problem is the opportunity to implement sustainable changes that will enhance the quality of our pedagogical system, more evidence-based, inclusive, responsive and transparent with clear set of policies and guidelines based on an innovative framework. The best way to move forward is the design and strategy that engages teachers, students, parents and school administrators to new teaching and learning situation allowing technology in education.

Molla (2021) stated that the crisis changes the way people think, behave, and they have tried to use the digital technology for communication and in education. Technology and social media, the fast triggering means of communication, internet-based technologies devices that are cheap and convenient tools of obtaining relevant information changed the pattern of the educational system (Gikas et.al., 2013 & Cavus et.al., 2009).

West (2021) acknowledge the social media and digital technology are helpful in daily life and integrating the use of these in education is essential than before. It provides more direct communication tool between students and teachers that becoming the new normal.

Bharath naik (2020) noted that many of the people have switched to the increasing use of social media websites and other applications. It is trending and have unnecessarily surged high than routine. Physical activity classes used social media to view samples of videos in fitness, dance and sports that benefitted individuals with myriads of advantages. It allowed people to stay in touch with each other online that reinforced face to face and share information about physical, mental and emotional well-being important in the domain of learning.

According to Dziuban et. al. (2018) that the digital technology is relevant on education setting. This blended learning modality impacting the teaching and learning environment that affects the student behavior and examine its transformation potential especially in physical and health literacy.

Kumi-Yeboah (2020) & Oliveira et. al. (2019) cited that education are inherently technology-based and combined with actual scenario learning, that has allowed teachers and students to interact beyond temporal and spatial limits. This new normal education has required educators to study and understand the use of emerging technology in aid to the new classroom setting.

According to LEARNING JOURNALS (2011-2022), there is a big demand for high quality education. The skills and knowledge they learn in school are very valuable from personal to peer relationships. The way teaching is delivered comes in a variety of forms. Furthermore, due to technology, there are a lot of ways teachers can impart education to their students and engage them in the learning process.

The digital technology has become ways to teaching and learning. The social media apps became important tools to help to manage the educational crisis (Abbas et.al. 2021). The social media application networking and idea-video-sharing allows the teachers and students interact effectively.

According to Cruz (2022) that the educational landscape set-up is shifting to combined in-person classes to distance learning enabled the adaptation of learning — combining classes with online and face to face learning modality. The physical education adopting the much enthusiasm exists to imagine how teaching practices can be enriched within the so-called ‘new normal.’ Capitalizing on the raised awareness of the many positive contributions of school physical education, a pressing priority is to now reengage students with physical activity in a manner that promotes enjoyable experiences and adaptive engagement with digital technology enhancing movement task activities (Blain et.al., 2022).

The researchers of this study recommended the adoption of the technology & social media applications as learning aid to enhance participation and knowledge of the students particularly in the different Physical Education class activities.

Statement of the Problem

The objective of the study was to determine the effects of the different social media applications as aid to Physical Education (PE) activities of students in tertiary education levels in this post COVID-19 pandemic.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following:

1. What are the respondents' PE subjects they engaged-in in this study?
2. What are the digital gadgets and social media apps they used as an aid to accomplish their activities and assignment outputs?
3. What are the live experiences beneficial to the participants of this study on the use of social media applications in accomplishing their task outputs?

Research Paradigm:

Figure1. Research Paradigm of the study

The Use of technology and social media this post Covid-19 pandemic motivated the students in physical education. Ledgerwood (2022) agreed that these educational tools effectively engage students as they can connect their knowledge in multiple contexts, decrease student boredom by providing them with the opportunity to become participants and co-producers in their learning (Faizi et al., 2013). Using this digital media involves students in learning activities that allow them to learn through doing, creating, and evaluating independently that takes the focus off the teacher and puts the students at the center of their learning experiences.

Methodology

Quantitative and qualitative methods were used in this study simultaneously. The SOP number 1 and 2 requires data of the participants' Physical Education subjects and the used of Social Media Applications which best be acquired using a descriptive quantitative design. These were done through the synchronous, asynchronous and face to face classes, presentation, demonstration and submission of the participants' task outputs. The study was done by first and second year students who took up PE subjects in the 1st Semester of the SY 2023-2024 in a locally funded university in the City of Manila. The qualitative approach was utilized to answer SOP number 3 which looked into the experiences of the participants on the benefits of using the social media apps to accomplish their task outputs. These were analyzed using a thematic approach to best provide a clear description of the experiences and benefits of using social media applications. This traditional dichotomy, between quantitative and qualitative method draw a meaningful pattern that is woven in contexts where the aim of the research is to highlight the fine line between innovation and change, in order to achieve the research objectives. (Marzano, et.al, 2015)

Results and Discussion

The results, discussion, and interpretation of data were presented and interpreted in conformity with the sequence of the statement of the problem.

Below is the result of the data collected and tabulated to show the number of participants in the different Physical Education Subjects, Technology/Gadgets and Social Media Applications they used.

Table 1

The Types of PE Subjects and the different Social Media Applications used by the participants in their activities and assignment outputs

Physical Education Subjects	Social Media Applications								Total %
	Canva	Capcut	Google Drive	Kine Master	Movavi Video	TikTok	Viva Video	You Tube	
Individual Dual Sport	3	0	5	4	0	0	3	0	15 12.5%
Team Sports	5	4	0	0	5	10	0	4	28 23.33%
Dance	2	0	6	5	0	0	4	4	21 17.5%
Physical Fitness	0	6	0	5	0	4	2	9	26 21.67%
Swimming Aquatics	3	4	8	0	2	5	4	4	30 25%
Total	13	14	19	14	7	19	13	21	120
%	10.83%	11.67%	15.84%	11.67%	5.82%	15.84%	10.83%	17.5%	100%

The distribution of data on Table 1 above shows that there were 120 Physical Education students who participated in this study, 15 or 12.5% of the participants engaged in individual and Dual Sports, 28 or 23.33% in Team Sports, 21 or 17.5% in Dance, 26 or 21.67% in Physical Fitness Activities, and 30 or 25% in Swimming and Aquatics.

Regarding the use of Social Media Applications according to the popular used of the respondents, there were 21 or 17.5% of students engaged with YouTube the highest, followed by Google Drive and TikTok with the same number of 19 each of 15.84%, the second. The third slot shared by Capcut and Kine Master with 14 or 11.67%. The fourth in rank shared also by the used of Canva and Viva Video with 13 or 10.83% respondents. The least popular in fifth rank is Movavi Video with 7 or 5.82%.

Table 2

The Types of PE Subjects and the Digital Gadgets used by the participants in their activities and assignment outputs

Physical Education Subjects	DIGITAL GADGETS						Total %
	Cell Phones	Cell Phones & Desktop	Cell Phones & Laptops	Desktop & Tablet	iPHONE	Tablet	
Individual Dual Sport	9	1	2	0	1	2	15 12.5%
Team Sports	19	3	4	2	0	0	28 23.33%
Dance	17	2	1	1	0	0	21 17.5%
Physical Fitness	18	2	3	1	1	1	26 21.67%
Swimming Aquatics	21	3	2	2	1	1	30 25%
Total %	84 70%	11 9.17%	12 10%	6 5%	3 2.5%	4 3.33%	120 100%

The distribution of data on Table above regarding the use of digital gadgets shows that the most used was Cell Phones with the total of 84 students or 70% rank first. Followed by the combination used of Cell Phones & Laptops with 12 students or 10%, second, the third in rank was the used of Cell Phones & Desktops with 11 or 9.17%, next was the used of Desktops & Tablets with 6 or 5%. Rank fourth was the used of Tablet with 4 of 3.33%. And the least used that rank fifth was iPhone with 3 or 2.5% respondents.

The Live Experiences of the Participants of this Study Beneficial on the use of Technology and Social Media in Accomplishing their PE Task Outputs

In the rigorous process of the best possible data gathering, the researchers observed and interviewed the participants, another, by reviewing, analyzing and validating the gathered information of their live experiences, the researchers clustered four (4) important themes that aided and helped the participants accomplishing assignments, lessons and task activities by using social media apps. The theme clusters were 1) open communication 2) quick information accessibility, 3) acquire informative videos and 4) search globally scientific references:

Open Communication

The students are enthusiastic in telling the benefits of communicating to the teacher and classmates outside the classroom or activity area, especially during the task assignment activities were difficult and need more clear instruction and information.

Faizi (2013) agreed that social media can help to aid students and teachers in communicating even when they are outside of the classroom. Use of social media platforms can provide with unlimited resources and texts from credible sources that they can utilize to their advantage in reports, projects, and presentations. They can also be used as a means of giving and receiving feedback at any time and can easily access comments made by teachers and peers within a few minutes.

Quick Information Accessibility

Most of the participants agreed that information were easily search thru the internet, in finding necessary information, meaning of words and explanation, related ideas, examples that helped them acquired knowledge, understand, articulated, explained and finished the task activity output.

Gikas and Grant (2013) pointed out that social media are both Internet and mobile-based tools that enable people to discuss and share information.

Acquire Informative videos

The students said that they have been benefited from many available video samples thru the social media, given them all necessary movement and steps in exercises, fitness activities, dances and sports skills that enable them to work independently or in group accomplishing physical education task skills.

According to McFarlane (2022) that social media videos are great options to get the target interest when compared to a wordy text, it is pretty simple to comprehend and analyzed to arrive to more concrete and substantial product of task outputs.

Search International Scientific References

The respondents say that they easily searched and found notable international references to supplement and validated their studies and assigned activity topics.

According to the study published by Hilbert et.al (2011), 95 percent of all information existing in the planet is digitized and most of it is accessible on the Internet and other computer networks. Castells (2014) also agreed that this computer networks, largely based nowadays on platforms of wireless communication, provides ubiquitous capacity of multimodal, interactive communication in chosen time, transcending space.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results and findings of this study, the students in different PE classes used different technology and social media to supplement and accomplished their assigned task activities. In their live experiences, because of the digital technology, they have an open communication with their instructors and classmates for activity questions, collaborations and clarifications. The internet gave them quick information access in relation to their subject matter definition, explanation, examples and background that helped them to easily understand and comprehend for finishing meaningful task output. They acquired informative videos in social media apps gave them visuals of steps, body movements, overall view of exercise, dances and sports skills help them for video recording, demonstration and presentation. They also searched international scientific references to support and validated their assignments and tasks. The researchers conclude that the technology and social media are supplementary and helpful in physical education classes in the post Covid-19 pandemic setting.

As Kenan, Jamia (2023) said, that with the remote learning and emerging technologies, social media is an integral part of education more than ever. There are many different ways to use social media for education inside and outside the classroom.

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